

Application of electrocoagulation treatment to meat industry wastewater

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INTRODUCTION

The meat industry generates wastewater highly loaded with organic matter. Application of traditional methods generally requires high investment and operation expenses can be a substantial hurdle to their implementation, particularly in small enterprises or developing nations. Therefore, it is necessary to find a treatment that is both, sustainable and environmentally friendly. In the last few years, electrocoagulation (EC) has attracted increasing attention in wastewater treatment. In this work, we investigate the possibility of the application EC process for the purification of meat industry wastewater.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Two sets of the EC experiments have been performed: (1) two aluminum electrodes Al(-)/Al(+)(EC1), (2) two iron electrodes Fe(+)/Fe(-) (EC2). The treatments were done in an EC unit which was made of borosilicate glass with a volume of 600 ml. For treatments aluminum and iron electrodes with the same dimensions of 10 cm x 5 cm x 0.1 cm were used. During the treatments the distance between the electrodes were 3 cm, the current strength were 3.33 mA/cm², the rotation speed were 280/min, the surface of the immersed electrodes were 30 cm², with the treatment time were 1 hour, and the volume of treated water was 0.5 l. The raw meat industry wastewater was characterized before and after each EC treatment determined: chemical oxygen demand (COD), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), total phosphorous (P), total nitrogen (N), pH, and turbidity.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The effects of electrocoagulation on meat industry wastewater were present in Table 1.

Parameters	E0	EC1	EC2
COD (mg O ₂ /l)	846	454	443
BOD (mg O ₂ /l)	433	215	206
Total P (mg/l)	2.26	0.12	0.14
Total N (mg N/l)	64.8	2.13	0.86
pH	6.66	7.93	7.82
Turbidity (NTU)	210	2.85	5.06

The experimental removal efficiencies for COD, BOD, total P, total N, and turbidity were 46%, 50%, 95%, 97%, and 99%, for aluminum electrodes and for iron electrodes removal efficiencies were 48%, 52%, 94%, 99%, and 98%, respectively. We can explain the reduction of COD, BOD, P, and N in treated water by the adsorption onto the surfaces of hydroxide precipitates, which are released by the electrodes. The high percentage of turbidity reduction is in accordance with the previously mentioned efficiencies of the tested treatments. The presented results show that there is no big difference in the achieved efficiencies between EC1 and EC2, therefore our recommendation is EC2 because Fe electrodes are cheaper.

CONCLUSION

EC holds immense potential to replace conventional wastewater treatment methods. In the future, we will focus on the optimization and improvement of the treatment in order to obtain water as a product that we can use for irrigating the surrounding agricultural areas or for reuse in the production process, which is very important from the point of view of the circular economy.

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